

INFLUENCE OF PSYCHOSOCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS ON HUMAN WORK AMONG SEAFARERS

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ABSTRACT:

Life satisfaction is not an average of the satisfaction experienced in the different life domains owing to the fact that humans have a tendency to weigh the different life domains differently. In effect, both the dispositional and situational factors interact and impact life satisfaction. It would be interesting to investigate life satisfaction as an outcome variable in the domain of management field for enhancing people's lives and therefore the impact of situational variables on life satisfaction is being investigated in the present study. Another important question that needs to be addressed is the identification of the factors that have an ability to influence life satisfaction

Keywords: Life satisfaction, Seafarer, Loneliness

Introduction:

Motivation of employees is core to effective human resource management. Motivation is the process that initiates, guides, and maintains goal-oriented behaviors. Motivation involves the biological, emotional, social, and cognitive forces that initiate behavior. In everyday usage, the term "motivation" is frequently used to describe why a person does something. Love or will to do (called motivation) depends on the strength of people's motives. Motives are the expressed needs and could be conscious or subconscious, which are always directed towards goals. Motivating people to perform, higher than their normal physical and mental capacities, and to keep them satisfied is a very complex function of management. Human behaviour is goal-directed. Motivation cause goal-directed behaviour. It is through motivation that needs can be handled and tackled purposely. This can be understood by understanding the hierarchy of needs by manager. The needs of individual serves as a driving force in human behaviour. Therefore, a manager must understand the hierarchy of needs. Organizational culture often develops over time and that it consists of deeper values and beliefs. Typical for a strong culture is that employees share the underlying values and beliefs of the organization. The organizational culture can have some impact on employee motivation.

The salient features or characteristics of motivation are as follows:

Human Aspect: Motivation is concerned exclusively with the human side of an enterprise. It means a process of stimulating human beings to make action for getting desired results. It creates will to work in the individuals. If a manager can enthuse, initiate and build up loyalty of the employees towards the achievement of the enterprise objectives with their willing cooperation, the sum total of all these will amount to motivation. Thus, motivation is a behavioural concept that directs human behaviour towards certain goals.

Psychological Concept:

Motivation is a psychological concept which generates feelings of certain needs within an individual. Human needs are nothing but feelings in the mind of a person that he lacks certain things. Such internal feelings affect the behaviour of the person. The workers, even with extraordinary abilities, will not be able to perform as

desired unless they are effectively motivated. Effective performance on the part of the workers can be said to be the end result of their abilities backed by proper motivation.

Need-Satisfying Activity:

Motivation is related to satisfying human needs. It can be effective only upon an accurate analysis of the workers' needs for the satisfaction of which they can be induced to work in the desired manner. A worker will perform the desired activity only so long as he sees his action as a means of continued fulfilment of his cherished needs. All motivated behaviour on the part of human beings is directed towards satisfaction or fulfilment of needs.

Motivation is Total not Part:

A worker cannot be motivated in parts. Each individual in the organisation is a self-contained and inseparable unit and all his needs are inter-related. These affect his behaviour in different ways. To be successful, motivation must take a worker as an indivisible unit and seek to appeal to all his urges and aspirations.

Financial and Non-Financial:

Motivation may assume several forms depending upon the needs, emotions, and sentiments of the workers. Broadly speaking, it can be classified as financial and non-financial. Financial motivation may be created by way of increasing wages, allowances, bonus, prizes, and other perquisites; while nonfinancial motivation may take the form of praise, recognition, providing greater responsibility or increased participation in decision-making.

Constant Process:

Human needs are infinite. As very aptly put by Abraham H. Maslow, Man is a wanting animal as soon as one of his needs is satisfied, another appears in its place. This process is unending. This means motivation cannot be a time-bound process. It is continuous.

Life Satisfaction:

The concept of Life Satisfaction marked through 19th century as a means for providing people with good life and influenced the development of Welfare State. By the late 20th Century, intellectuals attempted to find a proper definition of Life Satisfaction, envisioning the components of good life and its dimension. The term Quality of Life (QOL) was introduced in the 1960s. However, social indicators replaced the traditional economic criteria of welfare and satisfaction by mid-1980's saying that money cannot buy happiness.

Definition of Life Satisfaction:

Satisfaction is a latin word that means to make or do enough. Satisfaction with one's life implies contentment with or acceptance of one's life circumstances, or the fulfilment of one's wants and needs for one's life as a whole. In essence, life satisfaction is a subjective assessment of the quality of one's life. Because it is inherently an evaluation, judgments of life satisfaction have a large cognitive component. Life satisfaction is not only more stable and long-lived than happiness, it is also broader in scope. It is our general feeling about our life and how pleased we are with how it's going. There are many factors that contribute to life satisfaction from a number of domains, including work, romantic relationships, relationships with family and friends, personal development, health and wellness, and others. Life satisfaction measures are generally subjective, or based on the variables that an individual finds personally important in their own life. Your life satisfaction will not be determined based on a factor that you don't actually find personally meaningful.

The Importance of Life Satisfaction:

Life satisfaction is a desirable goal for humans and a happy life has been viewed as a basic human drive. Life satisfaction measures an individual's overall assessment of the life circumstances. Life satisfaction is not an

average of the satisfaction experienced in the different life domains owing to the fact that humans have a tendency to weigh the different life domains differently. In effect, both the dispositional and situational factors interact and impact life satisfaction. It would be interesting to investigate life satisfaction as an outcome variable in the domain of management field for enhancing people's lives and therefore the impact of situational variables on life satisfaction is being investigated in the present study. Another important question that needs to be addressed is the identification of the factors that have an ability to influence life satisfaction. Both dispositional variables (e.g., personality) and situational experiences have been shown to predict life satisfaction.

Literature review:

Neugarten et al. (1961) calls Life Satisfaction "an operational definition of 'successful aging'. Andrew (1974) states life satisfaction symbolizing an overarching criterion or ultimate outcome of human experience. Life satisfaction is an overall assessment of feelings and attitudes about one's life at a particular point in time ranging from negative to positive. It is one of three major indicators of well-being: life satisfaction, positive affect, and negative affect (Diener, 1984). Life satisfaction is characterized, in agreement with the cognitive theory, as "individual's cognitive judgment about comparisons based on the compatibility of their own living conditions with the standards" (Diener, Emmons, Larsen, & Griffen, 1985). Life satisfaction is a measure of a person's well-being, assessed in terms of mood, relationship satisfaction, financial status, achieved goals, self-concepts, and self-perceived ability to cope with life. Life satisfaction involves a favourable attitude towards one's life rather than an assessment of current feelings. Life satisfaction has been measured in relation to economic standing, degree of education, experiences, residence, and other factors. Life satisfaction is a key part of subjective well-being. Several factors influence subjective well-being and life satisfaction. Socio-demographic factors include gender, age, marital status, income, and education. Psychosocial factors include health and illness, functional ability, activity level, and social relationships. People tend to gain life satisfaction as they get older.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To measure the life satisfaction of seafarers.
2. To study the demographic profile of respondents in terms of experience and job category

Hypothesis:

H₀₁: If the parameters of the behavior determinants of seafarers are not significantly equally weighted by the respondents, to test which pair of parameters of the behavior determinants of seafarers are weighted significantly different and which are not, the null hypotheses are there is no significant difference between the pair of parameters of behavior determinants of seafarers concerned.

H₀₂: There is no variation of parameters of the Life satisfaction of seafarers over the classifications of the classification of demographic and employment related information Variable.

H₀₃: Both the parameters of the life satisfaction of seafarers are given equal priority by the respondents irrespective of their background information variables

Population/Universe and Sample:

Distribution of different categories of seafarers registered in the Visakhapatnam

Sr. No.	Designation	Population	Sample identified	Final Sample
1	Officer	700	70	69
2	Engineer	770	77	76
3	Staff/Trainee	1481	148	141
4	Cook/Others	260	26	25
	Total	3211	321	311

Systematic Sampling: Systematic sampling, sometimes called interval sampling, means that there is a gap, or interval, between each selection. It is often used in industry, where an item is selected for testing from a production line (say, every fifteen minutes) to ensure that machines and equipment are working to specification. Alternatively, the manufacturer might decide to select every 20th item on a production line to test for defects and quality or one customer might be selected initially in the beginning and every 5th customer might be selected for the sample. Alternatively, every customer entered the shop in a interval time of half an hour / one hour etc., may be included in the sample. This technique requires the first item / first person to be selected at random as a starting point for testing and, thereafter items / individuals selected as above will be included in the sample. Then using the questionnaire data will be collected surveys.Ex. Market researcher selecting every 10th person who enters a store, after selecting a person at random as a starting point will be the sample.

Table : 01

Responses based distribution of respondents on the statement “As a seafarer, I am happy with my life as a whole” under the parameter “Life satisfaction - Personal & Family satisfaction”

Response	No. of Respondents	Percent
Strongly disagree	13	4.2
Disagree	19	6.1
No idea	55	17.7
Agree	166	53.4
Strongly agree	58	18.6
Total	311	100.0

Table shows that, 4.2 percent of the respondents are strongly disagree, 6.1 percent disagree, 17.7 percent no idea, 53.4 percent Agree, and 18.6 percent of the respondents strongly Agree about the “As a seafarer, I am happy with my life as a whole” under the parameter “Life satisfaction -Personal & family satisfaction”.The responses on the statement “I feel that I am missing on the important moments and occasions in my life as I am away at sea” under this parameter is presented in Table.

Table: 02

Responses based distribution of respondents on the statement “I feel that I am missing on the important moments and occasions in my life as I am away at sea” under the parameter “Life satisfaction - Personal & Family satisfaction”

Response	No. of Respondents	Percent
Strongly disagree	5	1.6
Disagree	10	3.2
No idea	49	15.8
Agree	89	28.6
Strongly agree	158	50.8
Total	311	100.0

Table shows that, 3.9 percent of the respondents are strongly disagree, 16.7 percent disagree, 1.9 percent no idea, 44.7 percent Agree, and 52.4 percent of the respondents strongly Agree about the “I feel that I am missing on the important moments and occasions in my life as I am away at sea” under the parameter “Life satisfaction -Personal & family satisfaction”.The responses on the statement “I feel I am unavailable while on voyage for any health issues or emergency situations in the family” under this parameter is presented in Table.

Table: 03

Responses based distribution of respondents on the statement “I feel I am unavailable while on voyage for any health issues or emergency situations in the family” under the parameter “Life satisfaction - Personal & Family satisfaction”

Response	No. of Respondents	Percent
Strongly disagree	5	1.6
Disagree	3	1.0
No idea	14	4.5
Agree	99	31.8
Strongly agree	190	61.1
Total	311	100.0

Table shows that, 1.6 percent of the respondents are strongly disagree, 1 percent disagree, 4.5 percent no idea, 31.8 percent Agree, and 61.1 percent of the respondents strongly Agree about the “Before every voyage I undergo training programmes as per requirements” under the parameter “Life satisfaction -Personal & family satisfaction”. The responses on the statement “Networking problems and time zone differences act as a barrier in communicating with loves ones away from us” under this parameter is presented in Table.

Table: 04

Responses based distribution of respondents on the statement “Networking problems and time zone differences act as a barrier in communicating with loves ones away from us” under the parameter “Life satisfaction - Personal & Family satisfaction”

Response	No. of Respondents	Percent
Strongly disagree	1	.3
Disagree	8	2.6
No idea	40	12.9
Agree	136	43.7
Strongly agree	126	40.5
Total	311	100.0

Table shows that, 0.3 percent of the respondents are strongly disagree, 2.6 percent disagree, 12.9 percent no idea, 43.7 percent Agree, and 40.5 percent of the respondents strongly Agree about the “Networking problems and time zone differences act as a barrier in communicating with loves ones away from us” under the parameter “Life satisfaction -Personal & family satisfaction”. The responses on the statement “I am dissatisfied and unhappy because of the fact that I have to stay away from my family and loved ones for long periods of time, while on voyage” under this parameter is presented in Table.

Table: 05

Responses based distribution of respondents on the statement “I am dissatisfied and unhappy because of the fact that I have to stay away from my family and loved ones for long periods of time, while on voyage” under the parameter “Life satisfaction - Personal & Family satisfaction”

Response	No. of Respondents	Percent
Strongly disagree	4	1.3
Disagree	37	11.9
No idea	61	19.6
Agree	107	34.4
Strongly agree	102	32.8
Total	311	100.0

Table shows that, 1.9 percent of the respondents are strongly disagree, 11.9 percent disagree, 19.6 percent no idea, 34.4 percent Agree, and 32.8 percent of the respondents strongly Agree about the “I am dissatisfied and unhappy because of the fact that I have to stay away from my family and loved ones for long periods of time,

while on voyage” under the parameter “Life satisfaction -Personal & family satisfaction”. The responses on the statement “I am dissatisfied because of the lack of conjugal life for long periods of time” under this parameter is presented in Table .

Table: 06
Responses based distribution of respondents on the statement “I am dissatisfied because of the lack of conjugal life for long periods of time” under the parameter “Life satisfaction - Personal & Family satisfaction”

Response	No. of Respondents	Percent
Strongly disagree	5	1.6
Disagree	34	10.9
No idea	68	21.9
Agree	109	35.0
Strongly agree	95	30.5
Total	311	100.0

Table shows that, 1.6 percent of the respondents are strongly disagree, 10.9 percent disagree, 21.9 percent no idea, 35 percent Agree, and 30.5 percent of the respondents strongly Agree about the “I am dissatisfied because of the lack of conjugal life for long periods of time” under the parameter “Life satisfaction -Personal & family satisfaction”. The responses on the statement “As I am away at sea my spouse/family are burdened with all the domestic responsibilities” under this parameter is presented in Table..

Table: 07
Responses based distribution of respondents on the statement “As I am away at sea my spouse/family are burdened with all the domestic responsibilities” under the parameter “Life satisfaction - Personal & Family satisfaction”

Response	No. of Respondents	Percent
Strongly disagree	0	0.0
Disagree	30	9.6
No idea	49	15.8
Agree	107	34.4
Strongly agree	125	40.2
Total	311	100.0

Table shows that, 9.6 percent of the respondents are disagree, 15.8 percent no idea, 34.4 percent Agree, and 40.2 percent of the respondents strongly Agree about the “As I am away at sea my spouse/family are burdened with all the domestic responsibilities” under the parameter “Life satisfaction -Personal & family satisfaction”.The response on the statement “Long distance relationships are creating tensions in my family life” under this parameter is presented in Table ..

Conclusion

Seafarers go through various challenges on board with respect to work as well as personal life. Seafarers sacrifice their precious time, days and years staying away from their dear ones. It affects them physically and emotionally but still they keep going. Maintenance of work life balance is very important. The seafarer undergoes lot of pressure on-board that is work pressure, peer pressure, tensions in families and this causes stress to the seafarer as he is away from the family and is very much concerned about his dear ones. The 90% or more of the global economy is run by the seafarer as nearly whole of the world trade is carried on through the sea transport. Seafarers have to follow the toughest regulations and laws, which lead to enormous stress for them to ensure not only their own safety but also to comply with the rules and regulations. The work routines of a seafarer are monotonous on board due to the ever-increasing demands from the world market and increasing paperwork due to various laws and regulations. Extreme climatic conditions, toxic cargo exposures put the seafarers to face lots of health hazards. Apart from this the seafarers are at high risk of criminalization and abandonment when on board due to various country's unfair trials in an event of accidents and in many cases they lack proper help from even the government of their own country. In such situations even for small mistake seafarers pay very high price. Many seafarers sometimes working on old ships even have to stay in the substandard accommodation and with least communication facilities. Various ports due to security reasons deny the shore leave for them even after long voyages at sea. The seafarers indeed deserve great admiration for the tremendous work they perform.

Socially a seafarer lives to contradictory lives consisting of his workplace at sea and the other dealing with his personal life related to the families back home. A person's overall life satisfaction depends on his or her satisfaction in multiple domains in life such as family, finance, friendship, work, leisure, health and the like. Life satisfaction is a desirable goal for humans and a happy life has been viewed as a basic human drive.

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